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[Use Of Large Scale Yielding Corrections To Data From 0.16T CTsS]

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Technical memorandum - Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1 Introduction

The aim of the FRACTESUS project is to help establish the utility and limitations of small specimen fracture toughness measurements. In particular it aims to establish best practice guidelines and, if possible, to demonstrate the reliability of such measurements in the context of Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) safety cases and justifications. The reference specimen geometry is the miniature Compact Tension specimen, 10 mm x 10 mm x 4 mm, ($\sim 0.16T$ C(T) or $1/6T$ C(T)). This geometry is of particular interest to the nuclear industry as historic surveillance capsules include Charpy impact specimens, and up to eight $0.16T$ C(T) specimens can be manufactured from a single broken Charpy specimen (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Four $0.16T$ C(T) specimens as extracted from a broken half Charpy impact specimen.

One difficulty encountered when using small specimens is the small temperature range in which valid measurements can be used to support the derivation of the fracture toughness transition temperature (as defined by the Master curve T_0 [1]). Based on the range of reactor pressure vessel steels examined in [2], and illustrated in Figure 2, a significant proportion of test measurements on RPV steels are invalid when $T_0 - T_{\text{test}} < 10-20^\circ\text{C}$. More quantitatively, an estimate of the number of tests likely to result in invalid data was made by Ruggieri et al. [3] for precracked Charpy-shaped (10mm x 10mm single edge-notched bend, SENB) $0.4T$ specimens. Their results are shown in Table 1. (The calculations are based on multiple simulations of fracture according to the Beremin Local Approach model [4].) Between $T_0 - T_{\text{test}} < 20^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_0 - T_{\text{test}} < 10^\circ\text{C}$, between 14% and 57% of tests are predicted to be invalid, depending on the material characteristics. A larger proportion of invalid tests would be predicted for smaller, $0.16T$, specimens.

Figure 2 Master curve analysis [2] of 0.16T CTS data acquired by FRACTESUS partners from
 (a) A533B plate JRQ (initial $T_0 = -61.0$ °C, $\sigma T_0 = 4.5$ °C, $\sum n_i T_i = 10.78$, $T_{0,screen} = -52.9$ °C, Inhomogeneous) and
 (b) 15Kh2MFAA (initial $T_0 = -99.7$ °C, $\sigma T_0 = 4.5$ °C, $\sum n_i T_i = 13.2$, $T_{0,screen} = -78.9$ °C, Inhomogeneous)

Table 1: Fraction of tests on 10mmx10mm SENB specimens likely to produce invalid toughness measurements [3].

Toughness (MPa√m)	Number of specimens (N) required to obtain r=6 (Fraction lost)			Equivalent $T_0 - T_{test}$ (°C)
	n=10, $E/\sigma_y=500$	n=20, $E/\sigma_y=300$	n=5, $E/\sigma_y=800$	
50	6 (0)	6 (0)	6 (0)	66
60	6 (0)	6 (0)	6 (0)	45
70	7 (0.14)	6 (0)	7 (0.14)	29
80	8 (0.25)	7 (0.14)	8 (0.25)	18
90	11 (0.45)	7 (0.14)	14 (0.57)	7
100	16 (0.63)	8 (0.25)	17 (0.65)	0

Since toughness values acquired at $T_{test} < T_0 - 50$ °C are excluded from the derivation of T_0 , and censored if invalid when $T_{test} > T_0 - 50$ °C, the testing range within which test results can be expected to be both valid and uncensored is difficult to access without a good preliminary estimate of T_0 and/or a large number of specimens.

The invalidity of the toughness measurements is based on the loss of plane strain, small scale yielding (SSY) conditions, as described by the measured toughness (elastic-plastic stress intensity at failure, K_{Jc}) exceeding the limiting value

$$K_{Jc,limit} = \sqrt{\frac{E b_0 \sigma_y}{M}}$$

Equation 1

Where E =Young's modulus, b_0 = initial ligament, $W - a_0$ (W =specimen width, a_0 =initial crack length)
 σ_y =yield stress, M = non-dimensional deformation limit=30.

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If it were possible to correct for this loss of SSY, then a higher proportion of the tests on miniature specimens could be utilised and the difficulty of measuring T_0 with miniature specimens thereby reduced. This memorandum (in support of D3.4) describes the effects on data utility and T_0 estimates of using a method of correcting for the loss of SSY developed by Nevalainen and Dodds [5].

2 Large-Scale Yielding Correction

2.1 Methodology

All methods of correcting for large scale yielding (LSY) require the use of a model of fracture to identify the critical features of the stress and strain fields which determine the onset of fracture. The applied K required to achieve the critical conditions under LSY conditions is then equivalent to the applied K required to achieve them under SSY. Clearly, if the model is incorrect, then the critical condition is not described properly, and the equivalence is not properly identified. Many brittle fracture models exist and have been applied successfully to individual ferritic steels, although all suffer from some inability to apply to multiple ferritic steels. In consequence, different authors have used slightly different equivalence criteria to convert a K (or, rather J -value) measured under LSY conditions to one expected to be produced under SSY. For example, Rathbun et al. [6] and Kim et al. [7] both considered K values to be equivalent if, under both SSY and LSY, stresses above a critical value existed in the plane ahead of a crack over a critical area (based on the Curry and Knott model of failure [8]); Anderson and Dodds [9] and Baykal and Spätig [10] used the achievement of a critical stress over a critical volume; and Shimuzu et al. [11] used the achievement of a critical value of the Weibull stress (a particular convolution of stress and volume based on the Beremin model of fracture [4]). Several fracture models exist involving both stress and strain criteria, such as [12, 13, 14]. Ruggieri and Dodds [15] developed an extension of the Beremin fracture model to incorporate strain term based on Wallin et al.'s particle cracking model [14] and used this to perform LSY corrections. This model was also utilised by Li et al. for some of the steels used within the FRACTESUS project [16]. These corrections required finite element modelling. The work by Li et al. has been developed further to produce an analytical form [17], but this has not yet been published.

Nevalainen and Dodds [5] [18] also utilised a critical stress-equal area criterion to convert brittle fracture initiation toughness measurements in LSY to equivalent values in SSY. Like other workers, they used finite element simulations of specimens to determine the areas under given stresses in different specimens (in this case, CT and SENB specimens of different sizes). Conveniently for FRACTESUS, however, they extracted analytical expressions to summarise their results, and these can be implemented in a spreadsheet.

There are two aspects to Nevalainen and Dodds' correction: the first refers to the reduction in the driving force for crack extension caused by plasticity at the back face of the specimen and the edges of the specimen; the second refers to the reduction in the effective width of the crack front. Figure 3 shows how the driving force, J_0 (normalised by $b\sigma_0$, where $b=(W-a)$ and σ_0 =yield stress) is reduced from the nominally applied value, J_{avg} , as the applied loading increases. Figure 4 shows how the effective

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width, B_{eff} , as defined by (the stressed volume)/(the maximum cross-sectional area of the stressed volume) diminishes from B as the loading increases.

Figure 3. Toughness correction factors as supplied by Nevalainen and Dodds for (a) BxB SENB specimens (b) Bx2B SENB specimens (c) CTSS (CTSS with 20% side-grooves [18]).

Figure 4. Effective thickness correction factors as supplied by Nevalainen and Dodds for (a) SENB and (b) CT specimens [18].

Nevalainen and Dodds generalized the curves in Figure 3 to:

For $\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0} \leq \text{limit of proportionality}$, $\frac{J_0}{b\sigma_0} = \frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0}$

$\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0} > \text{limit of proportionality}$,

$$\frac{J_0}{b\sigma_0} = b_0 \left(\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0}\right)^{0.25} + b_1 \left(\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0}\right)^{0.5} + b_2 \left(\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0}\right) + b_3 \left(\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0}\right)^2 \text{ up to maximum}$$

Above maximum in polynomial $\frac{J_0}{b\sigma_0} = \text{Maximum value of } \left(\frac{J_{avg}}{b\sigma_0}\right)$

where b_n are fitting constants depending on the specimen geometry

Equation 2

They generalized the curves in Figure 4 to:

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$$\frac{B_{eff}}{B} = d_0 + d_1 \exp \left[\frac{d_2 J_{avg}}{b \sigma_0} \right]$$

where d_n are fitting constants depending on the specimen geometry

Equation 3

The values of the fitting constants for certain specimen geometries were calculated by Nevalainen and Dodds and are given in Table 2.

These expressions were implemented by Florian Obermeier of Framatome-Germany in the spreadsheet used to collect the FRACTESUS test data ("FRACTESUS_SEeD_V_0_3.xlsx"). The spreadsheet assumes that the J values for each specimen will be available. At this stage in the FRACTESUS project, not all the J values were inserted into the spreadsheet, so a slightly amended form of the spreadsheet was used for the calculations in the present work: the K values reported in [2] were used to calculate a J value which was then modified and converted back to an equivalent K. (At the same time, some typographical errors in FRACTESUS_SEeD_V_0_3.xlsx were corrected.)

The effect of Nevalainen and Dodds' (N&D) corrections are reported in the next section.

Table 2. Constants required for calculation of in-plane constraint loss according to Nevalainen and Dodds' method.

Geometry	%Side Groove	a/W	B/W	Limit of Proportionality	b_0	b_1	b_2	b_3	Max (J_{avg}/bs_0)	d0	d1	d2
SENB	0	0.5	1	0.008	-0.03645	0.215608	-0.06064	-0.56486	0.15565	0.63	0.27	-160
SENB	0	0.5	0.5	0.00706	-0.04732	0.265808	-0.17953	-0.50544	0.13144	0.45	0.45	-200
CTS	0	0.5	0.5	0.012	-0.04699	0.25299	-0.02889	-0.70659	0.16685	0.47	0.43	-140
CTS	20	0.5	0.5	0.012	-0.03418	0.196496	0.094021	-0.96813	0.15846	0.5	0.3	-100

2.2 Application to FRACTESUS data

2.2.1 JRQ

Table 3 shows the initial T_0 values and associated output of T0TEM analyses of the raw JRQ measurements, plus a column, S, showing the total number of samples tested. In most subsets, T_0 is such that all the data fall within the range $T_0-50^\circ\text{C}$ ($N=S$); in the combined data set only 3 measurements are excluded as being from tests performed below $T_0-50^\circ\text{C}$. In contrast, around 20% of the K measurements must be censored because of the anticipated loss of SSY ($r \sim 0.8N$). This is also illustrated in Figure 5.

Table 3. Original T_0 Measurements on JRQ

Laboratory	T_0 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	σT_0 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$T_{0,\text{scrn}}$ ($^\circ\text{C}$)	r	N	S	$\sum n_i r_i$	Inhomogeneous?
0.16T CTS								
UJV	-61.5	6.2	-46.4	18	24	24	2.45	Yes
HZDR	-64.9	6.7	-57.8	12	22	22	1.81	No
BZN	-58.0	7.2	-56.0	10	15	15	1.43	No
PSI	-50.4	6.6	-47.5	13	16	17	1.76	No
UKAEA	-65.4	6.4	-50.5	16	16	16	2.21	Yes
CRIEPI	-65.1	5.8	-53.3	23	24	24	3.18	Yes
Combined	-61.8	4.4	-53.1	93	115	118	12.8	Yes
Larger specimens								
1T CTS	-53.6	3.1	-41.3				10.9	No
pcCv	-65.6	6.0	-60.6	9	10		1.4	No
0.5T CTS	-42.2	6.8		11	14		1.14	No

T0TEM calculates the combined dataset to be inhomogeneous with the multimodal $T_{0m} = -54.77$, $\sigma T_{0m} = 23.47^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 5. Toughness measurements made on JRQ 0.16T CTs within FRACTESUS, showing data acquired in/outside test temperature range, censored and uncensored data.

Figure 6 shows the effect of applying the N&D LSY→SSY correction to the overall JRQ K-data at different temperatures. As expected, the reduction in K is greater at higher K and affects a higher proportion of the measurements at higher test temperatures. Adjustments are made even on data which are considered valid according to Equation 1. This is as expected, given that theoretical analyses generally lead to the prediction that values of $M \gg 30$ are required to avoid loss of SSY (e.g. [19]), while the choice of $M=30$ is based on experimental observations of the onset of visible LSY effects.

Figure 6 Effect of applying Nevalainen and Dodds' correction to K-values.

Without any other changes, the reduction in the higher K values has the effect of reducing the steepness of the temperature-dependence in the raw data and, thus, increasing the T_0 value derived by TOTEM for the combined JRQ dataset. This is illustrated in Table 4 and Figure 7. The increased T_0 leads the lowest-temperature measurements ($T_{\text{test}} = -110^\circ\text{C}$) to drop out of the usable range. N is thereby reduced by 14, but r is reduced by only 4, because several adjusted K values no longer need to be censored according to Equation 1 ($M=30$).

Table 4 shows that the trend of increased T_0 (and reduced N) after the N&D adjustment is also seen in the data subsets produced by individual laboratories³.

³ Considering the CRIEPI data, the adjustment means that the initial estimate of T_0 ($T_{0q,1}$) became -58.2°C , when all 24 data points were used. The six measurements acquired at -110°C were therefore outside the range of appropriate data and excluded in the next stage of the assessment. The resulting $T_{0q,2}$ became -61.6 , returning -110°C to the acceptable test range. This appeared to cause difficulties for the TOTEM software. Under these circumstances [1] requires that the average of the two T_0 values be used. The value of T_0 given for the CRIEPI subset in Table 4 is, therefore, the average of two calculations performed with NN's in-house methods. Since N and r were not affected by the presence/absence of the -110°C data, these are also given in the table.

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Table 4. Adjusted T_0 Measurements on JRQ.⁴

Laboratory	T_0 (°C)	σT_0 (°C)	$T_{0,scrn}$ (°C)	r	N	S	$\sum n_i r_i$	Inhomogeneous?
0.16T CTS								
UJV	-54.1	6.0	-47.2	20	23		2.52	Yes
HZDR	-56.9			13	22	22	2.07	
BZN	-51.4	6.7	-48.5	12	15		1.71	No
PSI	-44.29	8.2		8	8	17	1.02	
UKAEA	-51.6	6.7	-49.7	12	12	16	1.5	No
CRIEPI	-59.9			17	18 (24)	24		
Combined	-52.72	4.43	-46.31	89	101	118	11.66	Yes

Figure 7. Adjusted toughness measurements made on JRQ 0.16T CTSs within FRACTESUS, showing censored and uncensored data when M is left at 30.

⁴ TOTEM also failed to run for the adjusted PSI and HZDR data sets, but the reason for this has not yet been identified. This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant

Table 4 shows the effect of using the N&D adjustment without altering any other data analysis procedures. This is not, however, the most appropriate way to use the data. The purpose of the N&D adjustment is to correct for LSY, so correcting the data again for LSY, by censoring via Equation 1, is superfluous. If all the assumptions behind the N&D adjustment (i.e. the fracture criterion, the finite element simulation, the extraction of a generalized trend curve) are correct, then the adjusted values are SSY values, regardless of their magnitude, and it is appropriate to use no censoring criterion ($M=0$). If, on the other hand, some assumptions are incorrect, such that the adjustments are in the right direction but not of the correct magnitude, then it might be more appropriate to reduce the severity of the censoring, but not to remove it entirely.

The effect of reducing M is shown in Figure 8. Reducing M initially increases both N and r for the combined JRQ dataset, but these values stabilize as r reaches N . In consequence, T_0 also stabilizes. The data points added / returned to the calculation data set are at high K values and high test temperatures, so that the overall temperature-dependence of K in the adjusted data set becomes a little steeper and T_0 drops with decreasing M . For this, particular dataset, T_0 does not drop far enough to include the data acquired at $T_{\text{test}} \leq -104^\circ\text{C}$, so N remains lower after the adjustment than before. The stable value of r , however, is greater than that in the analysis of the original data.

Figure 8. Effect of adjusting K values according to N&D, then reducing M , on T_0 and the number of tests contributing to the calculation of T_0 . (Original values plotted at $M=35$ for clarity; calculations on original data performed with $M=30$.)

The stabilization of T_0 with decreasing M means that the calculated T_0 is not significantly affected by whether reduced censoring or no censoring is applied to the N&D adjusted data i.e. whether the N&D adjustment is correct or merely a good enough approximation to permit a reduction in M from e.g. 30 to 20. Table 5 shows the stable values of T_0 calculated from the adjusted data and reduced M , together with the value of M at which the value of T_0 stabilised. Comparing Table 5 with Table 3 shows that

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correcting K for LSY and decreasing M increases the utility of the combined JRQ dataset by increasing r. For the individual datasets, r may increase or decrease depending on whether the test temperatures were more strongly biased to low temperatures (closer to $T_0-50^\circ\text{C}$) or high temperatures (closer to T_0). For high test temperatures, more raw data must be censored ($r < N \sim S$) and the adjustment reduces censoring (r approaches N); for low test temperatures, few data are censored, but the N&D adjustment can raise T_0 such that data are lost to the $T_{\text{test}} < T_0-50^\circ\text{C}$ criterion ($r \sim N < S$).

Table 5. T_0 Values for JRQ calculated using adjusted K measurements and M value at which stable T_0 determined

Laboratory	T_0 (°C)	σT_0 (°C)	$T_{0,\text{scrn}}$ (°C)	M_{stable}	r	N	S	$\sum n_i r_i$	Inhom?
0.16T CTS									
UJV	-54.12	6.0	-47.24	20	23	23	24	2.93	Yes
HZDR	-58.26	5.7		15	22	22	22	3.29	
BZN	-53.10	6.7	-48.93	20	15	15	15	2.14	No
PSI	-44.29	8.2		30	8	8	17	1.02	
UKAEA	-51.60	6.7	-49.7	30	12	12	16	1.50	
CRIEPI	-59.49	6.2		25	18(24)	18(24)	24	2.25	
Combined	--53.70	4.4	-46.34	20	101	101	118	13.38	Yes

Comparing Table 5 and Table 3 shows that the adjustment does not affect the measurement uncertainty significantly: the average σT_0 is very marginally reduced by the adjustment. Figure 9 shows that the distribution of T_0 measurements from the different laboratories data is normal both before and after the adjustment, with the breadth of the distribution narrowing slightly after the adjustment ($\mu=-60.3^\circ\text{C}$, $\sigma=7.9^\circ\text{C}$ changing to $\mu=-53.4^\circ\text{C}$, $\sigma=6.4^\circ\text{C}$). The large and small specimen measurements overlap at 2SD in both cases, although the adjusted small specimen data provide a closer comparison to the large specimen data. (No adjustment has yet been performed on the large specimen data. It is assumed that any shifts in these data will be much smaller due to the larger ligament sizes (b values in Equation 2) in the larger samples.)

Figure 9. Comparison between large specimen data and original/adjusted 0.16T CTS data for JRQ.

2.2.2 ANP-5

The summary of the T_0 calculation made with the original data from weld ANP-5 taken from [2] (plus data from UKAEA produced after the report was delivered) is given in Table 6. The combined data distribution and Master curve limits are shown in Figure 10. The Table and Figure show that, overall, 3 data points were acquired at $T_{\text{test}} < T_0 - 50^\circ\text{C}$ and 16 (16%) were censored. The ANP-5 data in Figure 10 are much more inhomogeneous than those from JRQ, presumably because ANP-5 is a weldment. The multimodal T_0 parameters are $T_{0m} = -1.42^\circ\text{C}$, $\sigma_{T_{0m}} = 41.11^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 6. Original T_0 Measurements on ANP-5.

Laboratory	T_0 (°C)	σ_{T_0} (°C)	$T_{0,\text{scrn}}$ (°C)	r	N	$\sum n_i r_i$	Inhomogeneous?
0.16T CTS							
SCK-CEN	(+35.0)	11.6	xx	3	3 (10)	0.4	(Invalid)
FRA-G	-18.6	7.2	-15	10	13	1.36	No
HZDR	(+41.3)	xx	xx	0	0 (36)	0	(Invalid)
UKAEA	-45.2		-38.7	15	20	2.17	No
UC	-26.1	6.7	-8.8	14	16	1.8	Yes
Combined	-26.04	4.5	20.53	79	95	11.51	Yes
Larger specimens							
pcCv	-37.9	8.4		9	9	1	No
WOL (2T 4T 6T)	15.4	8.4		6	9	0.91	No

Figure 10. Toughness measurements made on ANP-5 0.16T CTSs within FRACTESUS, showing data acquired in/outside test temperature range, censored and uncensored data.

The effect of the N&D adjustment with reduced M is shown in Table 7 and Figure 11. The spread in the toughness data is reduced but the measurements are still clearly representative of an inhomogeneous material.

For the ANP-5 data set, T_0 is not always increased; the higher initial T_0 values are actually decreased by the adjustment, as illustrated in Figure 12.

Table 7. T_0 Values for ANP-5 calculated using adjusted K measurements and M value at which stable T_0 determined.

Laboratory	T_0 (°C)	σT_0 (°C)	$T_{0,scrn}$ (°C)	M_{stable}	r	N	S	$\sum n_i r_i$	Comment
0.16T CTS									
SCK-CEN	+46.4	14.8		30	2	2	10	0.27	Invalid
FRA-G	-30.5	6.6		15	13	13	13	2	
HZDR	+34.3	14.8		30	2	2	36	0.25	Invalid
UKAEA	-36.6	6.0		15	20	20	20	2.92	
UC	-32.3	6.1		15	17	17	17	2.41	
Combined	-24.9	4.5		15	85	85	88	11.77	

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Figure 11. Adjusted toughness measurements (1T equivalent) made on ANP-5 0.16T CTSs within FRACRESUS, showing Master curve bounds fitted when $M=15$, and highlighting data acquired below $T_0=50^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 12. Comparison between T_0 values derived from original data and from N&D adjusted data with reduced censoring.

Figure 13 compares the distribution of 0.16T CTS T_0 measurements with those from larger specimens. There is a greater range in T_0 measurements from large specimens of ANP-5 than of JRQ. Considering the ANP-5 T_0 values derived from the miniature specimen data, the original valid values are distributed This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant

about the lower large-specimen (pcCv) datum, while the original invalid values lie above the WOL datum. The N&D adjustment decreases the spread in the measurements from individual laboratories, most obviously for the valid measurements. This makes it clearer that the overall distribution of valid and invalid T_0 measurements is not normal. The valid adjusted T_0 values all lie between the measured large specimen values.

Figure 13. Comparison between large specimen data and original/adjusted 0.16T CTS data for ANP-5.

3 Summary and Conclusions

Toughness measurements performed with 0.16T CTSs have been corrected for loss of constraint by large scale yielding, using a method suggested by Nevalainen and Dodds. The aim of the adjustment was to decrease the number of invalid toughness measurements requiring censoring (r) during the derivation of T_0 .

The adjusted data are intended to represent the equivalent measurements that would have been acquired had the specimens remained in small-scale yielding. The adjusted data have, therefore, been treated as valid measurements, even when the adjusted toughnesses exceeded the limiting value for small-scale yielding according to ASTM E1921.

- The N&D method reduced the higher K measurements (including some measurements considered valid according to ASTM E1921).
- The values of T_0 derived from the adjusted data have been compared with those derived from the original 0.16T CTS data for two of the steels examined within FRACTESUS: JRQ and ANP-5.
 - When the original (valid) T_0 values were below -40°C , the adjustment raised T_0 , with the increase tending to be greater, the lower the original T_0 .
 - When the original T_0 values were higher than -30°C , the adjustment reduced T_0 .

- For T_0 measurements from individual laboratories, the uncertainty, σT_0 , was generally reduced by the adjustment, but only by a fraction of a degree ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). In this aspect, the use of the N&D adjustment does not lead to a significant gain.
- The laboratory-to-laboratory spread in T_0 values derived from adjusted data was smaller than that in T_0 values derived from the original data, by several degrees. This is a meaningful improvement resulting from using the N&D adjustment.
- The values of T_0 derived from the adjusted 0.16T CTS data have been compared with those derived from larger specimens.
 - The (valid) adjusted T_0 values always lay between the values measured on large specimens. The range of original (valid) T_0 values from miniature specimens extended beyond that from the large specimens, although all miniature specimen measurements were within 2σ of a large measurement. The adjustment thus leads to a slight improvement in comparability between small and large specimen data.

The desired increase in r was achieved for six of the nine valid sub-sets of data from individual laboratories. This improved the utility of the data sets. In three of the sub-sets from JRQ, however, the distribution of the data was such that, when the adjustment increased T_0 , additional measurements were associated with test temperatures below $T_0-50^{\circ}\text{C}$. The consequent decrease in the total number of measurements acquired within the acceptable temperature range (N) led to a decrease in r .

The N&D correction is based on the equivalence of a key feature of the crack tip stress field in large and small scale yielding. The definition of the key feature, in turn, depends on Nevalainen and Dodd's choice of a particular model of brittle fracture in low alloy steels. The N&D correction is, thus, only valid to the extent that the model is correct, and it is generally-agreed that a simple critical stress-critical area model of fracture is not widely applicable in low alloy steels. Nonetheless, the reduction in laboratory-to-laboratory variations in T_0 , and the improved match between miniature and large specimen data, indicates that the N&D adjustment possesses some validity and its use can improve the estimation of T_0 . It would be valuable to perform a similar exercise using the analytical form of the Ruggieri and Dodds/Li et al. [15, 16, 17] correction for a stress-and-strain-based fracture model, to assess whether the change in fracture model has a significant effect on the overall outcome of the correction procedure.

Current practice means that workers tend to aim to test miniature specimens at temperatures towards the middle and lower end of the range $T_0-50^{\circ}\text{C}$. This increases the number of tests required to produce a valid T_0 (increases the number of tests associated with a low weighting factor, n_i), but minimises the number of tests producing K_{Jc} values or ductile crack extensions above the validity limit. Applying the N&D adjustment to low- T_{test} -biased datasets can result in a reduction in the number of uncensored measurements by reducing the number of in-range tests (N). If the N&D (or any other) correction were completely reliable, protocols could be changed to increase the number of more highly-weighted measurements, reducing the chance of testing below $T_0-50^{\circ}\text{C}$. The present state of fracture modelling is such, however, that it is probably better to retain current protocols and use the N&D adjustment only to clarify the uncertainty associated with the censoring procedure when the fraction of censored data is high (e.g. $>20\%$) or to make use of data sets which would otherwise contain insufficient uncensored measurements to produce a valid estimate of T_0 .

Technical memorandum - Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

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